

ATTITUDES OF STUDENTS TOWARDS LEARNING GEOMETRY: A MIXED METHOD STUDY

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Attitudes of Students towards Learning Geometry: A Mixed Method Study

Julius Clyde C. Cabig,* Linagyn A. Gementiza-Cubio

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Attitudes towards learning the subject play a crucial role in students' engagement in class. Knowing the attitudes of students towards learning geometry can help identify the pedagogical approach and the support needed for their personal and professional development. However, research on the status of students' attitudes towards learning geometry is limited. The study aimed to describe the lived experiences of mathematics teacher education students in a local college on their geometry attitudes. This study engaged mixed method design, utilizing a parallel convergent approach. The participants of the study were the mathematics education students from first year to third year. There were 212 students who were randomly selected for quantitative and 14 for the qualitative. Based on the results of the study, it was determined that the status of student's attitude towards learning geometry is high. The results from the quantitative and qualitative converged when they were being corroborated. The results confirms that mathematics major students appreciate geometry for its practical applications in daily life and future careers. Their genuine interest in the subject fosters' confidence, leading to higher academic achievements. Moreover, the students find enjoyment in exploring the diverse and relevant topics within geometry, further enhancing their learning experience. The findings suggest that students should develop a strong grasp of geometry and cultivate a keen interest in learning the subject, students may regularly practice geometric problems, use extra learning materials like books and online resources, solve real-life geometry problems to see its practical uses, and stay curious and persistent when facing difficulties. This approach will help them build confidence and develop a positive attitude towards geometry.

Keywords: *attitudes towards geometry, convergent parallel, mixed methods, Philippines*

Introduction

One of the reasons that influences the students' achievements at school relates to their inner motivation. The attitudes of a students to the individual school subjects can be built or changed through the influence of the interaction with their own experiences. Geometry, the study of space and spatial relationships, is an important and essential branch of mathematics. In the study of geometry, students learn about geometric shapes and structures and understand how to analyze their characteristics and relationships. But the results of studies carried out by different researchers at different parts of the world show that students encounter a lot of difficulties while learning geometry. Many studies have been carried out on the attitudes towards mathematics with respect to some variables. Attitude towards geometry include liking, enjoying and interest in geometry, or the opposite, and at worst geometry phobia. This means that the students have to like geometry, enjoy the activities performed in geometry and have interest at heart for geometry (Bora & Ahmed, 2018).

Many students perform poorly in geometry and find the subject very difficult and uninteresting. In Taiwan, geometry is taught as a topic within mathematics in secondary education. Considerable research has reported that a large number of the students fail to develop an adequate understanding of geometry concepts, geometry reasoning, and geometry problem solving skills as they are expected to learn and encounter difficulties and performed poorly in geometry. Unfortunately, results of the present study demonstrate that many high school students in the study did not exhibit positive attitudes toward learning geometry. High school students seem to value geometry and view it as important, but they did not enjoy geometry or feel self- confident about geometry (Tsao & Tung, 2022).

Further, in a study conducted in the Division of Sagay City, Philippines, the results of the study revealed students find it difficult studying geometry. Students find mathematics, especially geometry, abstract and boring. Geometry is particularly challenging for them because they struggle with logical reasoning, especially in proving statements. They lack understanding of the subject, which hinders their participation and motivation during discussions and proofs. To add, environmental factors such as classroom noise and discomfort contribute to their difficulties. They also find the subject difficult due to their struggles with logical and critical thinking, as well as recalling necessary postulates and theorems. Overall, a combination of comprehension issues, lack of motivation, and environmental distractions contributes to their negative perception and difficulties with geometry (Parreño & Marpa, 2019).

Correspondingly, the motivation of students depends on their attitudes towards the subject. Many students perform poorly in geometry and find the subject very difficult and uninteresting. As student faces different types of problems in learning geometry, it is important to investigate the attitudes of students towards learning geometry. With these in mind, a study should be conducted which highlights attitudes of students towards learning geometry. In this regard, such study is adequately urgent since the attitudes of student's influences their motivation in which also create a big impact in their achievements. This study aims to determine the attitudes towards learning geometry of mathematics teacher education students through a mixed method research approach. The findings of this study could provide valuable insights for institutions looking to improve their mathematics education programs through innovative approaches to student's attitudes in learning geometry.

In this context, the students' attitudes towards learning geometry have been the subject of some studies, like the study of Kundu (2018)

entitled “Attitude of Secondary level Students towards Geometry”, the study investigated the attitudes of secondary level students towards geometry of secondary students under Purulia district, West Bengal, India; and the study of Bora & Ahmed (2018) entitled “Secondary School Students' Attitude Towards their Learning Geometry: A Survey of Diphu Town Secondary Schools”, the study investigated the difference in attitude of school students towards learning geometry by gender, and management of school. In addition, the study conducted by Pavlovicova (2015) entitled “The Attitudes of Students to the Geometry and Their Concepts about Square”, whereas it investigated the student’s conceptions about a square in accordance with their ability to solve the tasks that are assigned to the different levels of geometrical thinking and the connections between their results in the pre-test and the post-test to their attitudes to the geometry. These studies, however, conducted used only one research approach and was focused on the student’s attitudes in geometry in secondary level. In contrast, this study is different to the studies that have mentioned as this study specifically investigated the attitudes of mathematics teacher education students towards learning geometry in a local college in Barangay Maniki, Kapalong, Davao del Norte using a mixed methods research approach. This study aims to address this gap by examining the attitudes of mathematics teacher education students in learning geometry.

This research study intends to disseminate the findings of the mixed method study of student’s attitudes towards learning geometry among first year to third-year mathematics major students through hardbound copies distributed strategically within our academic community. Coordinating with the research office to arrange a formal presentation and distribute hardbound copies to faculty and staff during the event, fostering direct engagement and discussions. Additionally, ensuring that hardbound copies are prominently available in the library, making them easily accessible to students and researchers.

Research Questions

This study investigates the attitudes of BSEd-Math students, using a mixed methods research approach. The purpose of employing this approach was to gather both quantitative and qualitative data concurrently, merge the findings, and utilize them to address the research problem at hand. This research design allowed for the strengths of each data collection method to offset the limitations of the other, resulting in a more comprehensive understanding of the research problem through the combined analysis of both quantitative and qualitative data.

1. What is the status of the attitude of students towards learning geometry?
2. What are the lived experiences of BSEd-Math students with regards to their attitudes in learning geometry?
3. What insights can BSEd-Math students share with regards to their attitudes in learning geometry?
4. To what degree do the quantitative data corroborate with the qualitative data?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a mixed methods design, which involves the interlinking of qualitative and quantitative components to provide a more comprehensive account of the research problem. According to Halcomb and Hickman (2015), this integration is crucial for the rigor of the mixed methods research, and it can occur at any stage(s) of the research process. The term "mixing" refers to the process of linking the qualitative and quantitative elements to produce a fuller account of the research problem.

According to Bryman (2007), mixed methods research plays a vital role in research beyond mere validation. It enables the integration of multiple research methods, leading to a comprehensive and holistic perspective on the subject of study. This approach not only validates the research but also allows for a more profound understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. By combining the results obtained from different methods, researchers can potentially reveal new insights that might have been overlooked using a single-method approach.

The research design selected for this study was a convergent parallel mixed method. In this design, both types of data are collected concurrently and given equal priority. The survey was collected first, followed by one-on-one interviews. The two sets of data are analyzed separately, and the results are then merged, with the combined results being interpreted. This design is appropriate for the study as it aims to explore the convergence, divergence, contradictions, or relationships between the two sources of data (Hanson et al., 2005).

The convergent parallel design, also known as the convergent/triangulation design, involves the simultaneous implementation of both quantitative and qualitative studies during the same phase of the research process. In this design, both methods have equal priority, enabling them to play an equally important role in addressing the research problem. This design maintains the independence of the studies during data collection and analysis and then merges or combines the results during the overall interpretation (Petrosyan, 2018).

To gain a comprehensive understanding of the topic, this study was conducted using the convergent parallel design, which is a mixed-method design. The research process can be represented by two components: qualitative and quantitative (Morse, 1991). In a convergent parallel design, the researcher simultaneously conducts the quantitative and qualitative elements in the same phase of the research process, weighing the methods equally, analyzing the two components independently, and interpreting the results together. The researcher aims to triangulate the methods for corroboration and validation by directly comparing the quantitative statistical results and

qualitative findings. In the research process, two datasets were obtained, analyzed separately, and compared (Demir & Pismek, 2018).

Under a convergent parallel design, data from qualitative sources such as one-on-one interviews were collected alongside quantitative data obtained from a survey questionnaire. These data were analyzed simultaneously to uncover patterns and insights. For the qualitative phase, a discourse and thematic analysis were used in order to analyze the experiences of the mathematics teacher education students regarding their attitudes towards learning geometry. For the quantitative data, statistical analysis was employed to get the results on the profiling, experiences of the mathematics teacher education student, significant difference in the status and extent on how quantitative data corroborate qualitative data.

Consequently, this research employed a descriptive-comparative approach, which involved comparing and contrasting the collected results to draw meaningful conclusions. By utilizing both quantitative and qualitative research methods, this study aimed to know the status of attitudes towards learning geometry among mathematics teacher education students and provide a foundation for effective teaching strategies and techniques to enhance positive attitudes of the students towards learning the subject. Hence, the study contains both quantitative and qualitative research methods (Richardson, 2018).

In addition, phenomenological inquiry was utilized in this study to further develop the qualitative frame. This methodology assisted the discovery and understanding within the rich environment evolving within the experiences of the participants. A phenomenology focuses on the commonality of a lived experience within a particular group. Typically, interviews are conducted with a group of individuals who have first-hand knowledge of an event, situation or experience. Other forms of data such as documents and observations may also be used (Creswell, 2013).

On the other hand, the qualitative phase of this study utilized a phenomenological approach, which reflects an epistemological perspective that acknowledges the validity of multiple subjective truths. Qualitative data collection method such as one-on-one interviews was also employed effectively to glean insights into the social norms of the community, saturate the data obtained from in-depth interviews, and establish themes based on the researcher's collected data (Groenewald, 2004).

Participants

In this section, the distribution and profile in gathering quantitative and qualitative data from the participants and informants as well as respondents of this study are discussed. Additionally, the exclusion criterion is based upon the statuses of Mathematics major students and they must not be an irregular student of the said program on the first semester of the academic year 2023–2024.

Quantitative Phase

The respondents of this study were mathematics teacher education students from all year levels in Kapalong College Agriculture, Sciences and Technology during the second semester of S.Y. 2022-2023. They were chosen as the respondents because the study attitudes towards learning geometry of mathematics teacher education students in a Local College. Since the study purports to involve students who are in the mathematics education program in a local college, it would be fitting and valid to include mathematics teacher education students in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology.

Table 1.1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
First Year	119	78	36.79%
Second Year	50	33	15.57%
Third Year	43	28	13.21%
Total	212	139	65.57%

Further, the respondents were determined through sampling, specifically, stratified random sampling to establish randomness and maintain scientific rigor in the study. This method involves dividing population into smaller groups, or “strata,” and randomly selecting a sample from each stratum. The per-stratum samples are then combined to create an overall stratified random sample. An alternative to simple random sampling, stratified random sampling ensures that each stratum is represented in the sample and can provide more accurate results when analyzing subgroups within the population (Nguyen et al., 2020).

This sampling method was particularly appropriate in this study because the respondents, which are the mathematics education students was randomly selected based on strata, which in this case are all the year levels of the mathematics education program in Kapalong College Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. This also ensures that all of the respondents in the population have equal chances of being selected. The researcher wrote a formal request letter to the College Registrar and gained access to the population of mathematics education students from first year to third year. The researcher then gathered the data from the population of mathematics education students to compute the sample. After getting the data, the researcher sent the information to her statistician for computation of the study sample.

The study was conducted among students enrolled in the mathematics teacher education program from first year to third year. The institution has a total of 212 mathematics education students, consisting of 119 first year students, 50 second year students, and 43 third year students. However, the sample appropriate for the study was computed by the statistician, which included 78 out of 119 first year

students, 33 out of 50 second year students, and 28 out of 43 third year students. In total, 139 students were sampled out of the 212 students in the mathematics education program.

Qualitative Phase

In contrast, subject selection in qualitative research was purposeful. In this phase, non-probability sampling specifically purposive sampling technique was utilized. Participants were selected who can best inform the research questions and enhance understanding of the phenomenon under study (Kuper et al., 2008). Only 14 participants of mathematics teacher education students will be enjoined in the qualitative phase: fourteen (14) for in-depth interview. All of them should be a mathematics teacher education student at KCAST and he or she is a 1st year, 2nd year, or 3rd year student. It should be noted that participants in qualitative phase must not have participated in the data collection of quantitative phase.

Table 1.2. Profiles of the Participants

<i>Assigned Code</i>	<i>Sex</i>	<i>Year-Level</i>
IDI-01	Male	1st year
IDI-02	Female	1st year
IDI-03	Female	1st year
IDI-04	Female	2nd year
IDI-05	Female	2nd year
IDI-06	Male	3rd year
IDI-07	Female	3rd year
IDI-08	Male	1st year
IDI-09	Female	1st year
IDI-10	Male	2nd year
IDI-11	Male	2nd year
IDI-12	Female	3rd year
IDI-13	Male	3rd year
IDI-14	Male	3rd year

Instrument

Quantitative Phase

The researcher utilized an adapted survey questionnaire for geometry attitude which was adapted from Utley (2007). The said questionnaire used a Five-point Likert Scale which had the following indicators: the following indicators: usefulness, confidence, and enjoyment.

In a Five-point Likert Scale, participants were only required to rate and tick one box among one (lowest) to five (highest) in each question. Moreover, Likert Scale was good for measuring constructs, attitudes and stimuli which are not readily perceivable by human senses. Despite the questionnaire being adapted, it was still subjected to expert validation.

Qualitative Phase

As to the qualitative phase, a set of researcher-made grand tour questions was devised by the researcher and validated by the panel of experts. This was a set of open-ended questions that was developed based on the results of the survey. This was used as a compass for the in-depth interviews. Of all the participants who answered the survey questionnaire in the previous phase, fourteen (14) were purposively selected to undergo the IDI. Interviews were suitable in gleaning insights, stories, experiences, opinions and other useful information which could not be expressed with the use of numbers.

Procedure

There were several steps in the data collection process. The following procedures were followed during the conduct of the study:

Quantitative Phase

In the quantitative phase, an adapted questionnaire was used for the geometry attitudes of the students. It was administered to a group of Mathematics teacher education students who are in the school campus. In addition, the researcher wrote a letter of request to the school administrator, asking an approval to conduct the study to their respective school and students. The results were tallied, computed and analyzed to corroborate with the results of the qualitative data. The qualitative and quantitative phases of the study were done simultaneously.

Qualitative Phase

For the qualitative phase, a one-on-one interview was conducted to the identified participants in order to gather the lived experiences of these mathematics teacher education students with regard to their attitudes towards learning geometry. An interview guide was used

for the in-depth interview. Hence, to ensure authenticity of selection, the researcher invited through personal contact the informants and they were informed of the tasks to be and that includes the time set for everyone's convenience (Creswell, 2013).

Furthermore, in-depth or one-on-one interviews were also conducted to provide a valuable opportunity for exploring the perceptions of mathematics teacher education students regarding their experiences in their attitudes towards learning geometry. Fourteen (14) students were purposively selected for the interview, which were conducted by the researcher. The in-depth interviews were recorded, lasting from 20 to 1 hour, and were carried out using the face-to-face interaction.

Data Analysis

Quantitative Data Analysis

In the quantitative data analysis, descriptive statistics such as the mean were utilized to assess the average responses of the respondents. The survey data, which was collected, served as the basis for in-depth analysis. Upon retrieval of the questionnaires, the data was tallied and treated accordingly. The survey data was further analyzed using Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for both descriptive and inferential statistics. These statistical treatments were applied to ascertain the status of mathematics teacher education students.

Qualitative Data Analysis

Regarding the qualitative data analysis, the researcher employed coding and thematic analysis. This involved examining the patterns and themes that emerged from the utterances or statements of the participants/informants during the one-on-one interviews. The themes were formulated with the purpose of analyzing the lived experiences of mathematics teacher education students in their attitudes towards learning geometry. The data was carefully analyzed to identify and extract relevant themes that shed light on the research objectives and provide insights into the participants' experiences in this context.

Ethical Considerations

In order to uphold the trust of the mathematics teacher education students from KCAST, the study prioritized their safety, anonymity, complete protection, and confidentiality as key concerns. Measures were taken to ensure that these ethical considerations were carefully addressed, aiming to maintain the trust of the participants throughout the course of the study.

The researcher diligently adhered to ethical principles including respect for persons, beneficence, justice, obtaining informed consent, and maintaining confidentiality to ensure that ethical standards were met. These principles guided the conduct of the study in a responsible and respectful manner, prioritizing the rights and well-being of the participants (Mack et al., 2005).

Respect for persons is an ethical principle that underscores the importance of treating research participants with courtesy and respect and acknowledging their autonomy in decision-making regarding their participation in a study (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013). This principle necessitates providing participants with comprehensive information about the study and ensuring that they have a clear understanding of the research and any potential risks or benefits. Obtaining informed consent is a crucial aspect of adhering to this principle, as it signifies voluntary agreement based on an informed understanding. By upholding the principle of respect for persons, the researcher can ensure that the study is conducted ethically and in a manner that honors the rights and autonomy of the participants.

Before conducting the interviews, the researcher obtained permission from the participants and arranged the schedule in advance to avoid conflicts with their classes or other obligations. This was done to ensure that the researcher's presence would not disrupt the participants' schedules and to avoid the need for rescheduling or canceling the interviews.

During the conduct of my study, I established a respectful and courteous relationship with the participants and obtained their permission before recording the conversations. I also allowed the participants to ask questions at any time and maintained the confidentiality of the in-depth interviews and focused group discussion. In addition, the participants will have the right to refuse to answer sensitive questions. By establishing rapport and acting with courtesy towards the participants, I was able to conduct the study in an ethical and respectful manner.

Consent is a fundamental aspect of research ethics and serves as a way to show respect to research participants. By obtaining informed consent, the participants are made fully aware of the objectives and purpose of the research they are being asked to participate in. Written consent was obtained from the participants, certifying their approval to take part in the in-depth interviews. They were provided with information about the results and findings of the study, ensuring transparency and keeping them informed (Creswell, 2012).

To ensure the ethical conduct of the study, I provided the participants with letters of permission and consent that outlined the details of the study, including the methods, design, and procedures. These letters were intended to help the participants understand the nature of the study and make informed decisions about whether to participate. Participants who decided not to participate were allowed to leave without any explanations and were assured that their data would remain confidential. The researcher will also inform the participants that they have the rights to be informed of the result of the study. By following these ethical guidelines, the researcher was able to ensure that the study was conducted in a responsible and respectful manner.

Beneficence, as an ethical principle, emphasizes the commitment to minimize risks and maximize the well-being of research

participants. In this study, efforts were made to ensure the safety and protection of the participants. Anonymity of the interviewees was maintained to prevent any potential risks to their privacy and confidentiality. All files of information were properly secured and not left unattended or unprotected (Bricki & Green, 2007).

Furthermore, the data collected from this research study was used only for the purposes outlined in the study. However, the results of the study may also be shared or disseminated through channels such as presentation to the institution, publication in scientific forums or journals, or presentation at conferences, either locally, nationally, or internationally. By disseminating the results of the study, the researcher aims to share the findings and contribute to the broader knowledge base in their field of study.

Confidentiality towards the data, results and findings including the safeguard of participants, different techniques were used. Meaning, all personal identities of the participants were hidden and not shown. All materials including audio records, encoded transcripts, notes, soft and hard copies of data and others should be eliminated right after the data is analyzed (Maree & Westhuizen, 2007).

To protect the participants' identity and ensure compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012, I used discrete coding to denote each participant's responses. This measure involved carefully phrasing any information that could potentially identify the participants in terms of their name, gender, ethnicity, or employment/location to avoid violating their anonymity. By using proper coding and other measures, I was able to protect the participants' identity and ensure that their privacy was respected.

Justice in the conduct of this study was upheld by ensuring that the rights of the participants who identified themselves as mathematics teacher education students were respected. Given that the study aimed to investigate the attitudes towards learning geometry of mathematics teacher education students, no rights of minor students were violated. To ensure fairness and equal opportunity for participation, the researcher utilized random sampling and purposive sampling techniques. Mathematics teacher education students were not coerced into participating and were given the freedom to decline if they so choose. In recognition of their contribution, tokens were provided to the participants, and they were duly credited for their involvement in the research, contributing to the overall success of the study. Additionally, justice was ensured by including only relevant utterances of the participants related to the research objectives and accurately transcribing them (Munhall, 2012 & Scott, 2013).

Results and Discussion

Status of Attitudes of Students Towards Learning Geometry

The result of the survey conducted are presented here. The overall mean, the items with the highest and the lowest rating per indicator were given emphasis.

Table 2. *Status of Attitudes of Students Towards Learning Geometry*

No.	Items	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Usefulness			
1.	Needing geometry for my future.	4.16	High
2.	Seeing ways of using geometry concepts to solve everyday problems.	4.09	High
3.	Often seeing geometry in everyday things.	4.11	High
4.	Needing a firm understanding of geometry in my future work.	4.21	High
5.	Seeing geometry as a practical subject to study.	4.25	High
Category Mean		4.16	High
Confidence			
1.	Being sure that I can learn geometry concepts.	4.24	High
2.	Being confident I can get good grades in geometry.	3.91	High
3.	Being sure of myself when doing geometry problems.	3.87	High
4.	Being confident that if I work long enough on geometry problem, I will be able to solve it.	4.17	High
5.	Having a lot of confidence when it comes to studying geometry.	3.96	High
Category Mean		4.03	High
Enjoyment			
1.	Continuing to think about geometry when I leave class with a geometry question unanswered.	4.03	High

2. Saying geometry is fun.	4.11	High
3. Saying geometry is an interesting subject to study.	4.26	Very High
4. Enjoying solving geometry.	4.13	High
5. Saying geometry has many interesting topics to study.	4.33	Very High
Category Mean	4.17	High
Overall Mean	4.12	Moderate

Geometry Attitudes. There are three indicators to measure the status of geometry attitudes as perceived by the math major teacher education student's in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences and Technology. These are usefulness, confidence, and enjoyment. As shown in Table 2, the participants' overall status of perceived geometry attitudes was rated high with overall mean of 4.16. This means that the mathematics teacher education students manifested oftentimes their attitudes towards learning geometry.

Usefulness. In terms of usefulness, the category mean is 4.16, which is describe as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Among the items under this indicator, Item No. 5- Seeing geometry as a practical subject to study got the highest mean of 4.25 which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. On the other hand, the lowest item rated by the participants were the Item No. 2- Seeing ways of using geometry concepts to solve every day problems with a mean of 4.09. This rating is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Confidence. The confidence as experienced by the students got the lowest category mean of 4.03 but still described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. Item No. 1- Being sure that I can learn geometry concepts garnered the highest rating with a mean of 4.24, which is described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the students. Conversely, the Item No. 3- Being sure of myself when doing geometry problems got the lowest mean of 3.87 and described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students.

Enjoyment. The enjoyment as experienced by the students got highest category mean of 4.17, which is described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students. In this category, Item No. 5- Saying geometry has many interesting topics to study rated with a mean of 4.33 and described as very high. This means that it is always manifested by the students. On the other hand, Item No.1- Continuing to think about geometry when I leave class with a geometry question unanswered got the lowest mean of 4.03 and described as high. This means that it is oftentimes manifested by the students.

The Lived Experiences with Regards to Attitudes Towards Learning Geometry

There are eight essential themes which are created based from the in-depth interviews of the participants on the first research question. Before the presentation of the results from the interviews and discussions, profiles of the participants for the qualitative data collection are presented in table 3. The table represents the participants' profiles for the qualitative phases are selected purposively following the inclusion criteria: he or she must be a 1st year, 2nd year, or 3rd year mathematics major education student in KCAST. Based on the table, the profiles are divided into participants' gender, and year level.

Table 3. Participant's Information

Assigned Code	Pseudonym	Gender	Year Level
IDI-01	Participant 1	Male	1st year
IDI-02	Participant 2	Female	1st year
IDI-03	Participant 3	Female	1st year
IDI-04	Participant 4	Female	2nd year
IDI-05	Participant 5	Female	2nd year
IDI-06	Participant 6	Male	3rd year
IDI-07	Participant 7	Female	3rd year
IDI-08	Participant 8	Male	2nd year
IDI-09	Participant 9	Male	2nd year
IDI-10	Participant 10	Female	2nd year
IDI-11	Participant 11	Male	2nd year
IDI-12	Participant 12	Female	3rd year
IDI-13	Participant 13	Male	3rd year
IDI-14	Participant 14	Male	3rd year

Further, Table 4 deals on the lived experiences of the mathematics teacher education students in their attitudes towards learning geometry. The essential themes which emerged from the transcriptions of the participants' responses for the research question number one are consisted of overarching themes which are summarized in the said table.

Having a favorable disposition towards learning geometry. In the context of student’s geometry attitudes, some of the experiences experienced by the students are the excitement in learning geometry, understanding the practical role of geometry, confident in learning geometry, and enjoyment in learning geometry. It was being mentioned by the participants that by the excitement, understanding the practical role of geometry, confidence, enjoyment results a positive and active engagement of students in learning geometry. Each attitude towards learning geometry has encouraged and motivates the interest of students towards learning the subject.

Table 4. *The Lived Experiences with Regards to Attitudes Towards Learning Geometry*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/ Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Positive attitudes of students in learning geometry	Recognizing the excitement in learning geometry is fueled by discovering new concepts	Excitement in learning geometry	Having a Favorable disposition towards learning geometry	Self- Determination Theory
	Acknowledging problem-solving in geometry ignites excitement			
Effect of interactive and engaging teaching strategies	Identifying geometry's challenges brings excitement and fulfillment			
	Perceiving the mastery of geometric skills to teach it in the future	Understanding the Practical Role of Geometry		
	Recognizing Geometry as essential for daily life and future careers			
	Valuing the acquired knowledge for building something in relevance to geometry			
	Observing new learnings in geometry enhance happiness of students	Enjoyment in learning geometry		
	Recognizing relevance of geometry in the surroundings provides students' enjoyment			
	Discovering the usefulness of geometry in daily life contribute to students' satisfaction			
	Utilizing tangible models enhance understanding of abstract concepts	Integration of 3D models enhances understanding	Utilizing Interactive Teaching to Boost Learning	Constructivist Theory
	Recognizing clear teaching with illustrations and 3D demos boosts learning			
	Appreciating teaching methods using physical objects aids understanding	Elevating Understanding through Practical Teaching		
Identifying teaching with real-life examples boosts understanding				
Acknowledging effective teaching when it includes practical applications				
Recognizing geometry as more fun and relatable when taught using real-life examples	Simplifying Complexity deepens Understanding			
Acknowledging breaking complex problems to simpler one enhances students' engagement				
Recognizing step-by-step teaching in geometry boosts understanding				
Acknowledging breaking complex ideas into digestible parts results better understanding				
Influence of Support Given from teachers, peers, or family members	Recognizing enthusiastic teachers increased student's motivation	Enhancing Learning with Passionate Teaching and Quality Materials	Support System's Impact on Boosting Learning	Bandura's Social Learning Theory
	Identifying effective teaching support motivates and fosters a positive attitude in learning			
	Recognizing motivating materials in learning boost efficiency and confidence			
	Recognizing peer support greatly enhances understanding of geometry	Peers' encouragement motivates students in learning geometry		
	Identifying peer interest in geometry motivates individuals to engage with the			

subject
 Acknowledging peer competition and
 emotional support drive motivation and
 learning
 Recognizing family support and Family Support Bolsters
 motivation play a crucial role in shaping Learning
 one's attitude towards geometry
 Identifying family financial support
 boosts engagement in academic projects
 Acknowledging family provides
 emotional support and motivation during
 difficult times

Excitement in Learning Geometry. This is the first code on the first probed issue. Students expresses common response on the excitement they feel in learning geometry. Most of them stated that they felt excitement due to new learnings and challenges in dealing with geometry.

Consequently, Participant 1 recognized the excitement in learning geometry due to discovering new learnings. As a result of this, they felt happiness as they absorb new ideas and concepts of the subject. This highlights the importance of willingness in fostering positive attitude towards the subject. He stated that:

“My attitudes towards learning geometry are excited and happy. Excited because everytime na mag discuss si sir there’s always new learning na masabtan namo then happy because sa pagpadayon ana there are times masabtan nako ang mga gidiscuss ni sir and it feels wonderful sa pamati kay nasabtan nmo.” (IDI-01)

(My feelings toward learning geometry are enthusiastic and joyful. I feel excited because every time our teacher discusses it, there's always new knowledge that we can understand, and I feel happy because as we continue, there are moments when I grasp what our teacher discusses, and it feels wonderful to understand it)

Moreover, students wish all subjects like geometry due to the excitement they felt towards the subject. By solving challenging problems in geometry, student’s interest’s boost in dealing with geometry. It is clear that the challenges in solving geometry problems enhanced the excitement of students as they find dealing with it interesting. As Participant 14 cited that:

“In terms of learning geometry sometimes ga wish ko na unta geometry nalang tanan subject because I find it exciting. It is exciting by the fact that murag syag ga solve ug problem like mangita ug mga sides, pangitaon ang area and I find it interesting in things like that.” (IDI- 14)

(Regarding learning geometry, sometimes I wish that it were the only subject because I find it thrilling. It's thrilling because it feels like solving problems, like finding sides or calculating areas, and I find interest in tasks like that)

Lastly, challenges faced in learning enhances excitement of students towards dealing the subject. As a result, they felt happiness and by learning the concepts, the subject become easy to deal with. By embracing the challenges in solving geometry problems, students feel excitement which enhances their engagement towards the subject. As Participant 2 cited that:

“When learning geometry, I’m always excited and I’m challenged every time na maglearn ko ug geometry and I’m happy because makita nko sa subject na challenging at the same time mas sayon lng if ma gets nmo ang concept sa geometry.” (IDI-02)

(When learning geometry, I'm always excited, and I'm challenged every time I learn it. I'm happy because I see the subject as challenging, yet it becomes easier once you grasp the concepts of geometry)

Understanding the Practical Role of Geometry. This is the second code on the first probed issue. Interviewed participant’s imparted that they perceived the usefulness of geometry in daily life and in their future careers. Most of them stated that learning geometry is useful as we are dealing with geometry in our surroundings and especially in the future as they will become future mathematics educator.

Consequently, Participant 14 identify the usefulness of learning geometry as we are unconsciously dealing with it and mastering the subject is essential as he wants to become a mathematics educator in the future. As a result of this, he wants to learn more about geometry as he wants to impart his knowledge about geometry to his future students. This highlights the importance of knowing the usefulness of geometry to be motivated towards learning the subject. He stated that:

“I consider geometry all around the world and we are unconsciously using it. For example, in terms of estimating, solving, and scaling objects. I think it is useful in my future careers especially as an educator that I must master or harness my skills because I will teach it someday to my future students.” (IDI-14)

(I see geometry everywhere in the world, and we use it without even realizing. Like when we guess sizes, solve problems, or make things bigger or smaller. I believe it's important for my future job, especially as a teacher. I need to get really good at it because one

day I'll be teaching it to my students.)

Moreover, understanding geometry is crucial for everyday life and future careers, particularly in fields like architecture, engineering, and teaching. It emphasizes the importance of geometry in various aspects of life, including problem-solving, spatial reasoning, and communication skills, and underscores its relevance in both professional and educational contexts. As Participant 12 said that:

“Ang geometry is ma perceive nko sya na relevant man sya sa atong daily life or sa future career especially atong career na atong pilion is architecture or engineering important jud kaayo na sweto kag geometry. Even teaching kay need mana nato I teach sa atong students.” (IDI-12)

(The geometry is something I perceive as relevant in our daily life or future career, especially if the career we choose is architecture or engineering. Geometry is very important, as it provides a solid foundation for these fields. Even in teaching, we need to incorporate geometry into what we teach our students)

Lastly, acknowledging the relevance of geometry in daily life as we are surrounded with geometric concepts and dealing with it unconsciously. By emphasizing the usefulness of geometry to deal with real-life problems the students are motivated to learn the subject. Recognizing the use of geometry boosts the student's engagement and gain positive attitude towards the subject. As Participant 5 cited that:

“Ma perceived nko ang relevance sa geometry sa akong daily life or future career kay wala ta kabalo sa atong palibot ga deal na diay ta ug geometry and makause jud ta geometry, maapply nato sya sa pagsolve sa real- world problems dli lng sa mathematics but also sa real- life situation.” (IDI-05)

(I perceive the relevance of geometry in my daily life or future career because we are unaware that we deal with geometry in our environment, and it turns out that we actually use geometry, we can apply it to solve real- world problems, not only in mathematics but also in real- life situations)

Confident in Learning Geometry. This is the third code of the first probe issue. Participants in in-depth interview express confidence in learning geometry. Most of them confirmed that they are confident to learn the concepts in the subject. Moreover, students recognized in-depth learning boost their confidence which led to high scores in geometry assessments.

Consequently, Participant 5 confidently stated that he can learn geometry concepts as he pushes himself to study. Studying the lesson, especially difficult ones, boost the student's confidence to gain good grades in the subject. As a result, students become motivated and happy towards learning the subject. This highlights the importance having confidence in learning geometry. He stated that:

“Ang akoang attitude towards learning geometry is ginakuan gyud nko akong kaugalingon na magstudy kaya I can say na I can learn geometry concepts and confident pod ko na makakuha ko ug dagko na grado sa geometry since ginabanatan man nako ug study labi na ang mga concepts na maglisod ko ug sabot and by that I am motivated sa akoang ginabuhat kay malipay man ko kay dagko akong scores sa exam ug sa mga quiz.” (IDI-05)

(My attitude towards learning geometry acknowledges my own dedication to studying. Thus, I can confidently say that I can grasp geometry concepts, and I am confident that I can achieve high grades in geometry since I devote myself to studying, especially the concepts that I find challenging to understand. This motivates me because I am pleased with my high scores on exams and quizzes)

Moreover, confidence is a product of hard work in learning the subject. Studying geometry enhances students' confidence in solving geometric problems. By that, students are confident that they can acquire good grades in learning geometry. This emphasizes the impact of studying to students' confidence and to students' performance. As Participant 7 cited that:

“I feel confident in learning since I am fun of studying geometry so I know that I can answer the problems and I know I can get good grades in learning geometry.” (IDI- 07)

(I feel confident in learning because I enjoy studying geometry, so I believe I can solve the problems and achieve good grades in geometry.)

Further, students' confidence in geometry was driven by their prior knowledge. Reading books related to geometry boosts students' confidence towards the subject as he become more familiar with geometric terms. This shows the impact of eagerness to learn and student's prior knowledge their confidence in learning. As Participant 14 stated:

“I'm also quite confident in learning geometry because when I was in high school, I always read books about geometry and reading that book boost my confidence as I am familiar with geometric terms.” (IDI-14)

(I'm also quite confident in learning geometry because when I was in high school, I always read books about geometry. Reading those books boosted my confidence as I became familiar with geometric terms.)

Lastly, student's shows confidence to learn geometric concepts as the they are interested towards the subject. Students are interested to learn the subject which results to good grades in quizzes. This shows the relationship of student's interest to learn and confidence to their performance in learning geometry. As Participant 2 said that:

“I am confident also na makatuon sa mga geometric concepts since interested ko sa subject. Ganahan man gud ko magtuon gyud ug geometry kaya dagko ko ug score sa quizzes namo.” (IDI-02)

(I am also confident that I can learn geometric concepts because I am interested in the subject. I really enjoy studying geometry, which is why I consistently score high on our quizzes.)

Enjoyment in Learning Geometry. This is the last code on the first probed issue. Mathematics major students imparted that they felt enjoyment in learning geometry. Most of them mentioned that the new learnings, the relevance, and by discovering the relationship of shapes and the usefulness of geometry daily life contribute to students’ enjoyment towards the subject.

Consequently, Participant 9 mentioned that due to broad topic of geometry that are confusing especially in 3D figures student’s felt diverse attitude towards the subject. Somehow, observing new learnings in geometry enhances happiness of students. This emphasize that learning new things satisfies the student’s and motivates them to learn more about the subject, especially in geometry. He stated that:

“My attitudes towards learning geometry are diverse siya, klase-klase siya na attitude tungod kay geometry kay broad sya na topic ug confusing siya pag abot sa 3D figures. In some ways attitude nako kay happy pod siya na maka learn kag bag.o nabutang.” (IDI-09)

(My attitudes towards learning geometry are diverse because geometry is a broad topic and it can be confusing when it comes to 3D figures. In some ways, my attitude is positive because it makes me happy to learn something new.)

Moreover, Participant 13 enjoyed learning geometry due to its relevance in our surroundings. Knowing the relevance of the subject in our daily life motivates students to learn and enjoy the subject. This emphasize that recognizing the relevance of geometry in the surroundings provides students’ enjoyment. She said that:

“I am more enjoyed learning or studying with the full grasp of the lesson because I can relate with the topic because it is relevant sa atoang palibot especially we are surrounded with geometrical shapes and also geometrical concepts that really aligns with the geometrical theories na atoang ma encounter in our daily lives as a mathematics teacher education student.” (IDI-13)

(I enjoy learning or studying more when I fully understand the lesson because I can relate to the topic, especially since it is relevant to our surroundings. We are surrounded by geometrical shapes and concepts that align with the geometrical theories we encounter in our daily lives, especially as a student studying mathematics education.)

Lastly, discovering the relationship of shapes and the usefulness of geometry in daily life contribute to students’ satisfaction. Students enjoy in understanding things about geometry which motivates students to learn more about the subject. This entails the impact of enjoyment in student’s motivation in learning geometry. As Participant 11 cited that:

“I did enjoy learning geometry. It helps me discover the relationship of shapes and the usage of it in daily life. Learning something and understanding things about geometry helps me enjoy and it's a satisfaction for me to learn anything.” (IDI-11)

(I enjoyed learning geometry. It helped me discover the relationships between shapes and their everyday applications. Understanding geometry enhances my enjoyment of learning, and it's satisfying for me to grasp new concepts.)

Utilizing Interactive Teaching to Boost Learning. In response to the in-depth interview, the teaching strategies like Integration of 3D models, real-life application, and breaking complex concepts into simpler one is interactive and engaging in learning geometry. These teaching strategies create impact to student’s attitudes towards learning geometry.

Integration of 3D Models Enhances Understanding. This is the first code for the second probed issue. From the in-depth interviews, it was experienced by students that the integration of 3D models was engaging and effective in learning geometry. This teaching approach motivates and provides enjoyment in students learning geometry.

Similarly, as geometry deals more on spaces, planes, and figures integrating 3D type examples is appropriate and effective teaching method. Students appreciate the use of solid figures as a tool for examples in the discussion, made them more enjoy and motivated towards learning geometry. Utilizing tangible models enhance understanding of abstract concepts like space, planes, and figures, making learning more effective. As Participant 10 said that:

“Geometry is more on spaces, planes, figures, so it is more appropriate and more effective for me if the teaching method or approach is somehow connected to learning by doing and the 3D type. Example, if a teacher wants a student to understand the area or the volume of a certain figure, it is very much appreciated if there is also a 3D figure or there is a structure itself not only the typical type na we will draw it on a white board. It is more appreciates if there is a solid figure in front of the students for them to really understand what it is.” (IDI- 10)

(Geometry primarily deals with spaces, planes, and figures. Therefore, I find it more appropriate and effective when the teaching method or approach involves hands-on learning and 3D models. For example, if a teacher wants students to understand the area or volume of a certain figure, it is much appreciated if there is a physical 3D model or structure present, rather than just drawing it on a whiteboard. Having a solid figure in front of students greatly enhances their understanding of the concept.)

Furthermore, recognizing teaching methods that articulating the concepts properly and demonstration through 3D figures catches students' attention and excitement towards learning geometry. Teaching geometry with illustrations is essential for students understanding. This indicates the importance of clear teaching with illustrations and 3D demos to boosts students learning. As Participant 14 said that:

“The teaching methods where they are articulating properly the concepts and demonstrating it through illustrations or even 3 dimensional figures.” (IDI-14)

Lastly, student's engagement boost when teachers integrate 3D models in teaching subjects like geometry. Integrating 3D models influence students in a positive way. Mathematics major students appreciate teaching methods using physical objects or 3D models aids understanding, especially in geometry, boosting engagement and learning towards the subject.

“Ang mga teaching methods na gina apply sa maestra makaingon ko effective is mag integrate sila or mag present ug mga physical objects or mga model's kay para makita sa estudyante kung unsay hitsura sa mga gina discuss namo, kay dba ang geometry kay more on shapes sya so maka ingon ko na ang mga effective na teaching method kay kanang mag present ug mga 3D models, let's say magdiscuss mo ug squares or rectangles, so ang mga maestra pwede magpresent ug mga libro mga ing.an... So, kami na students maimpluwensyahan mi in a positive way pag mag present sila ug 3D objects kay naa may engagement ang mga students like magunitan man nila ang mga objects so dli lng taman sa imagination kung unsay hitsura sa mga shapes na ginadiscuss like makita jud namo ang mga objects.” (IDI-06)

(The teaching methods that the teacher applies, I can say, are effective when they integrate or present physical objects or models so that students can see the appearance of what we are discussing. Because geometry is more about shapes, so I can say that effective teaching methods include presenting 3D models. For example, if you're discussing squares or rectangles, teachers can present books or other objects... So, we as students are positively influenced when they present 3D objects because students are engaged, they can touch the objects, not just rely on imagination to understand the shapes being discussed, we can actually see the objects.)

Elevating Understanding through Practical Teaching. This is the second code for the second probed issue. Interview informants imparted that teaching geometry with real-life application enhanced student's engagement. Student's recognized teaching with real-life examples and practical applications boost understanding and enjoyment.

In connection with that, student's encountered teaching methods in geometry where teachers integrate practical teaching in which exciting and engaging approach. Practical applications encouraged student's to enhanced their understanding in geometric concepts. This teaching approach equipped students with real-life examples which boosts understanding by highlighting relevance. As Participant 4 said that:

“Another teaching methods or approaches na akong na encounter pod is gi na apply ang isa ka topic into real life since mas ma realize man gud nimo if unsa sya ka relevant sa real life.” (IDI-04)

(Another teaching method or approach that I have encountered is applying a topic to real life because you realize its relevance better when you see how it applies in real life.)

Likewise, effective teaching when it includes practical applications, as merely explaining concepts without demonstration lacks impact. Students will not understand the full grasp of geometric discussion contextually. It is important to teach with real world application for better learning experiences. As Participant 7 cited that:

“The teaching methods that I consider effect is application because if more on context lng ka mga information pero dli nmo sya ma pakita sa students, wala jud na sya. Like sa amoa as mathematics students as explain-explain lang without even doing something or walay ipakita na model lisod sya sabton. It very important if magtudlo kag geometry naa kay example na ma show nmo sa students kay dako kaayo syag tabang since application real world experiences. So pag matry nila sa application na part so mas effective.” (IDI-07)

(The teaching methods that I consider effective involve application because if it's just about providing information without showing it to the students, it's useless. Like in our case as mathematics students, if it's just explaining without any practical application or without showing a model, it's difficult to understand. It's very important when teaching geometry to have examples that you can show to the students because it greatly helps in understanding through real-world experiences. So when they try the application part, it's more effective.)

Lastly, students recognized geometry as more fun and relatable when taught using real-life examples. Utilizing real-life problems enhances student's enjoyment and eagerness to listen in discussions. This highlights that the relevance of the subject to real-life situations boost understanding towards the subject. As Participant 8 said that:

“Mas ganahan ko maminaw ug mga geometric subject if mag base ang teacher sa real-life situation. Mas makalingaw sya.... Since kung maggamit ug real life situation or relevance na problems involving geometry, mas ganahan ka maminaw since marelata man nmo in real life. Naa man gud kasagaran na ikaw mismo naa ka sa situation na gihatag sa example edi marelata nmo sa imong kaugalingon and then mas masabtan pajud nmo.” (IDI-08)

(I prefer listening to geometric subjects more when the teacher bases them on real-life situations. It's more enjoyable... Because when real-life situations or relevant problems involving geometry are used, you're more interested because you can relate it to real life. Often, you find yourself in situations similar to the examples given, so you can relate to them, and then you understand them better.)

Simplifying Complexity Deepens Understanding. This is the third code of the second probe issue. From the in-depth interviews, it was experienced by students that teaching approaches that simplifying complex concepts into simpler one deepens students understanding in learning geometry.

In that sense, teaching methods of breaking complex problems to simpler one enhances students' engagement. This approach in teaching geometry boost students understanding concepts especially when it comes to real-life examples. With this approach, students learning in geometry will be motivated and enjoyed towards the subject. As Participant 3 cited that:

“Breaking the complex problems into simpler one kay para masabtan and ga incorporate ko ug real life examples para makarelate ko ug mas engaging pod para sa akoa.” (IDI-03)

(Breaking down complex problems into simpler ones so that I can understand, and I incorporate real-life examples to relate better and make it more engaging for myself.)

Additionally, utilizing step-by-step teaching in geometry boosts understanding from basics to advanced problem-solving. While learning geometry, students expressed that they understand the lesson well if the solving process was presented in a step-by-step method. This presents the importance of dealing the lesson from basic to complex ideas. As Participant 4 stated that:

“The most effective or engaging na teaching methods na akong na encounter while learning geometry is the step- by-step na method kay mas mapasabot niya ang akong pagtuon ana na concept since gina present niya ug unsaon sya pagsolve gikan sa basic to difficult.” (IDI-04)

(The most effective or engaging teaching method that I have encountered while learning geometry is the step- by-step method because it helps me understand the concept better as it presents how to solve it from basic to difficult.)

Lastly, students' engagement towards the subject boost when they fully grasp the concepts of the lesson. Breaking complex ideas into digestible parts fosters cohesive understanding and effective learning, especially in teaching geometry. This emphasizes that students learning experience becomes worth it if they deal geometric problems by breaking complex ideas into simpler one. As Participant 13 cited that:

“Ang pinakalast jud nako na makuan no kay breaking complex ideas or lessons into small parts. Like dli gud nmo sya isahon ug sabot, Imo lng sa gud I break break Ang lesson para ang imong idea kay mag connect- connect sya aron dli sya magkatibulaag ug imo syang isahon.” (IDI-13)

(The last thing I really appreciate is breaking complex ideas or lessons into small parts. Because you can't just grasp it all at once, you have to break the lesson so your idea can connect and not get confused by trying to grasp it all at once.)

Support System's Impact on Boosting Learning. In response to the in-depth interview, the participants mentioned that they are motivated and engaged towards learning geometry because of the people who always encouraged and supported them. The support system boosts the student's attitudes towards learning geometry.

Enhancing Learning with Passionate Teaching and Quality Materials. This is the first code for the third probed issue. Participants mentioned that passionate teaching and materials quality enhanced students learning in geometry. Having this kind of support from teacher motivates students to learn more about the subject.

In relation to that, students recognized supportive influences, like enthusiastic teachers, positively shape attitudes towards learning geometry, fostering increased motivation among students. Teacher's motivation to discuss the lesson influence the morality of the students. This highlights the effect of teacher's attitudes to student's attitudes towards learning geometry. As Participant 6 cited that:

“Their supports no naka affect pod sya sa akong attitudes towards leaning geometry in a positive way. Let's say ang teachers makita nato sa ila na motivated sila na magtudlo sa atoa, so mas ma motivate pod mi.” (IDI-06)

(Their support also influenced my attitudes towards learning geometry in a positive way. Let's say we see that the teachers are motivated to teach us, so it also motivates us.)

Additionally, effective teaching support boosts motivation and fosters a positive attitude towards learning, particularly in understanding complex concepts like geometry. Efficient teachers boost students understanding towards the subject. As a result, students become motivated and confident towards learning geometry. As Participant 6 stated that:

“Ang support sa teachers na ginatarong nila ug explain ang concepts para makatuon ko mas ma motivated ko, my positive gamay akong attitude towards learning geometry. Nakasabot naman gud ko maong ganahan nako mag learn na mas palawman pa lang mga concepts.” (IDI-12)

(The support from teachers in properly explaining the concepts so that I can learn, motivates me more, and it positively affects my attitude towards learning geometry. I understand, that's why I enjoy learning even more as the concepts become clearer.)

Lastly, motivating materials in learning, like those provided by teachers in geometry, boost efficiency and confidence. Materials provided by teachers motivates students to be engaged in the subject. This support builds confidence to students to eagerly learn geometry. As Participant cited that:

“Like the teachers provide materials which motivated me when learning geometry because I think the learning is efficient when there are materials included in the learning process which builds me confidence.” (IDI-14)

(The teachers provide materials that motivated me when learning geometry because I believe learning is more efficient when materials are included in the process, which boosts my confidence.)

Peers' Encouragement Motivates Students in Learning Geometry. This is the second code for the third probe issue. Interview participants imparted that support from peers motivates students in learning geometry. Moreover, most of the participants mentioned that with their circle of friends they maintain to be engaged towards the subject. Peer support contributes towards understanding and mastery of geometry.

Consequently, peer support greatly enhances understanding and mastery of geometry. The positive impact of peers can motivate the students engagement and performance towards learning geometry. This shows the vital role classmates and friends play in academic achievement. as Participant 13 stated that:

“There is a positive impact ang mga support gikan sa akong mga peers. .Mao na sya ang rason ug nganong dako kaayo ug tabang akong mga classmates and also mga amigo aron mas masabtan nko ang subject matter or ang lesson sa geometry.” (IDI-13)

(The support from my peers has a positive impact. That's why my classmates and friends are a great help in understanding the subject matter or lessons in geometry.)

Moreover, students are often influenced by the interests of their peers, especially when it comes to subjects like geometry. If peers are interested in geometry and frequently discuss it, a student might feel inclined to become interested too in order to relate to them and avoid feeling left out of conversations. This social pressure can motivate learners to learn about the subject even if you weren't initially interested. As Participant 11 said that:

“In peers, if the peers are really interested to geometry, then you would be likely to be interested because you want to relate to other people especially in your peers that you always be within with your circle of friends. If they're talking about geometry, you would be likely left behind of their topic so you would be likely to learn the subject.” (IDI-11)

(In terms of peers, if they're genuinely interested in geometry, you're more likely to be interested as well because you want to connect with others, especially your peers who are part of your social circle. If they're discussing geometry and you're not engaged, you might feel left out of the conversation, prompting you to learn the subject.)

Lastly, peers can affect how much students want to learn. If the peers are competitive, students sometimes feel like pressure, but it actually makes them want to learn more. They don't want to fall behind in their learning journey. Also, their friends give them emotional support, which stops them from feeling down when they struggle. This support makes them even more motivated to study geometry. As Participant 4 cited that:

“Next sa peers, since akong peers man kay very competitive pero usahay maka presure sya but in a good way since mas ma inggan yo man ka na maki pag competensya sa ilaha na makatuon pod kay dika ganahan na ma left behind pod sa ilahang journey... Isa pod, paras atong sa akong peers nagahatag man silag emotional support so ang imohang learning dli sya depressive kanang parehas anang ma left behind ka sa uban so mas ma motivate pa ang akong pagtuon sa geometry.” (IDI-04)

(Next, regarding peers, since my peers are very competitive, sometimes it can be pressuring but in a good way because it motivates me to compete with them in learning. You don't want to be left behind in their journey. Also, some of my peers provide emotional support, so your learning experience doesn't feel depressing, like feeling left behind by others, which further motivates me to study geometry.)

Family Support Bolsters Learning. This is the third code for the third probe issue. From the interview conducted, participants affirmed that support from family motivates students in learning geometry. Also, participants stated that family members lift their confidence especially when dealing with challenges in learning geometry. Family support play a crucial role in shaping students' attitude towards learning geometry.

Consequently, students recognized that the family's influence may not directly relate to geometry itself but their encouragement and motivation significantly impact the student's attitude towards the subject. The support from family boosts learner's confidence, helping them persevere through challenging mathematical problems and believe in their ability to succeed. This emphasized that family support and motivation play a crucial role in shaping one's attitude towards geometry, transcending its direct impact on mathematical skills. As Participant 13 stated:

“When it comes to the family dli jud sya directly sa geometry naka positively affect but in my attitude towards geometry, it is all about the motivation that they are giving to me na naghatag sila ug motivation sa akoa na magpadayon when encountering mathematical challenges na lisod kaysya I address. They’re helping me through motivation jud, ilahang gina lift akong confidence na I can do or I can answer that specific problem.” (IDI-13)

(When it comes to the family, they don't directly affect me positively in terms of geometry, but in my attitude towards geometry, it's all about the motivation they give me. They provide motivation for me to continue when encountering mathematical challenges that are difficult to address. They're helping me through motivation, boosting my confidence that I can tackle or solve that specific problem.)

In addition, in the family there is a mutual understanding that engaging in geometry projects is beneficial because it leads to financial assistance. The students are motivated to comply with these projects because their family provides financial support when they have financial needs. This financial assistance incentivizes them to actively participate in geometry projects to maintain the support from their parents. As Participant 6 said that:

“Tapos ang sa family, kaning geometry kay more on naa sad niy mga projects, pag naa koy pangayuon sa ila na mga financial assistance mutabang ang akong pamilya so mas ma engaged ko na mu comply sa mga projects kay tungod naa may financial assistance na ginahatag akong parents.” (IDI-06)

(And when it comes to the family, with geometry involving more projects, whenever I need financial assistance, my family helps out. This makes me more engaged in completing the projects because of the financial assistance provided by my parents.)

Lastly, in the family, there is emotional support during times of difficulty or when understanding towards geometry is lacking. This support helps the students cope with breakdowns and motivates them to persevere. Additionally, the family provides learning materials to aid in studying geometry, demonstrating their commitment to the person's education and well-being. As Participant 2 cited that:

“Sa family pod every time na naa mi dli masabtan and naga break down mi naa sila to support emotionally, gina motivate mi na makayara ug gina providan ko ug learning materials na mas makahelp pa sa akong pagtuon sa geometry.” (IDI-02)

(In the family, every time we encounter difficulties and feel overwhelmed, they are there to provide emotional support. They motivate me that I can do it and provide me with learning materials that further aid my study of geometry.)

Insights shared with Regards to Attitudes of Students Towards Learning Geometry

Displayed in the Table 5 are the responses of the participants in regards to the insights that can be shared of mathematics major students with regards to their attitudes towards learning geometry.

There are three essential themes which are drawn out from the in-depth interview of the participants for the second question. The essential themes consisted codes based from the issues being probed which are summarized in the table.

Table 5. *Insights Shared with Regards to Attitudes Towards Learning Geometry*

<i>Issues Probed</i>	<i>Core Ideas</i>	<i>Code/ Categories</i>	<i>Essential Themes</i>	<i>Theoretical Support</i>
Importance of different study habits	Recognizing regular group study sessions among peers	Essence of	Improving Geometry Learning with Collaborative and Digital Tools	Constructivist Theory
	Identifying studying geometry together for better support and understanding	Employing Collaborative Study Sessions		
	Recognizing group study fosters effective knowledge exchange			
	Understanding the purpose of geometry is essential since it simplifies comprehension	Importance of Studying the Fundamental Concepts of Geometry		
	Recognizing the essence and applications of geometry enhances motivation.			
	Understanding the fundamentals of geometry is essential			
	Tutorial videos help math students grasp geometric concepts	Utilizing Online Platform is Necessary to Enhance Learning		
Learning facilities and materials	The combination of self-learning with traditional and online instruction boosts learning outcomes			
	Utilization online resources for effective self-learning proximity to construction disrupts focus			
	Learning environment affects attitude and focus	Disruptive learning environment	Challenges in Learning Environment and Resources	Resource Dependency Theory
	Noisy classrooms hinder geometry analysis and discussion			
Insufficient books and 3D models hinder geometry learning	Insufficient Learning Resources			
lack of tools and limited information impede geometry learning				

<p>Interactive pedagogy in learning</p>	<p>poor conditions and scarce materials hamper learning Skilled instructors and innovative methods Interactive demonstrations and discussions teachers efficiency makes students attentive Geometry teaching strategies should adapt to diverse learning speeds Teaching imperfections prompts varied strategies and differentiated instruction Identifying step-by-step instruction in geometry enhances comprehension and retention Interactive methods like 3D models optimize geometry teaching effectiveness Real-world problem-solving aids comprehension and application of concepts Hands-on learning surpass passive teaching methods for deeper understanding</p>	<p>Teachers' Efficiency in Teaching Utilizing varied Strategies to cater Diverse Learners Employing Student-Centered Teaching Method</p>	<p>Interactive Pedagogy in Geometry Learning Constructivist Theory</p>
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Improving Geometry Learning with Collaboration and Digital Tools. This is one of the emerging themes from the responses of the participants from their in-depth interview with the categories of essence of employing collaborative study session, importance of studying the fundamental concepts of geometry, and utilizing online platform is necessary to enhance learning. The participants mentioned that to enhance learning in geometry it is effective when students employ collaborative study sessions, understands the fundamental concept of geometry, and utilization of online platforms.

Essence of Employing Collaborative Study Sessions. This is the first code of the issue probed. Students stated that employing collaborative study sessions can enhance understanding towards learning geometry. By having group study sessions, students find better support and understanding where students foster effective knowledge exchange.

Consequently, students and their peers engage in group study regularly to motivate each other and enhance their learning of geometry. Learning geometry with friends avoid boredom which will lead to better understanding the subject. Since geometry is a challenging subject to learn, a collaborative study session can make it easier. As Participant 2 stated that:

“In terms sa peers naa mi group study permente in order for us na ma motivate mi ug mas magtuon pajud about sa geometry.” (IDI-02)
 (In terms of peers, we have regular group study sessions to motivate ourselves and to further our study of geometry.)

Moreover, geometry is not an easy subject to learn, there’s many complex concepts that needs full attention. That is why it is important to seek support or studying with peers to gain better understanding and comprehension, especially when facing challenges in learning geometry. Study buddies will boost student’s motivation and confidence in learning geometry. As Participant 8 said that:

“Mangita sila ug support or kauban mag study kay two heads are better than one, pag naa kay dli masabtan siguro masabtan sa imong kauban. It is good to find a partner or group na makatabang sa imoha in learning geometry.” (IDI-08)
 (They look for support or study companions because two heads are better than one. If there's something you don't understand, maybe your companion will understand. It's good to find a partner or group that can help you in learning geometry.)

Lastly, studying with others is important because no one person knows everything. When studying together, everyone can share what they know, helping each other understand better. This collaborative approach not only enhances comprehension but also enriches the learning experience, making it highly effective for students learning geometry. As Participant 10 stated that:

“Doing group study is also important because maybe you know a thing but it is really impossible that you know everything. It's an exchange of knowledge that is very effective for me.” (IDI-10)

Importance of Studying the Fundamental Concepts of Geometry. This is the second code of the first issue probed. Understanding the fundamental concepts of geometry is crucial because they form the building blocks upon which more complex geometric principles and problem-solving techniques are constructed. Mastery of these foundational ideas provides a solid framework for further exploration and application. By grasping these fundamental concepts, students can develop critical thinking skills, spatial reasoning abilities, and a deeper appreciation for the inherent beauty and logic of geometric principles.

Consequently, when sharing knowledge about geometry with other students, it's important to emphasize the purpose of studying geometry. Understanding the purpose behind learning geometry makes it easier for students to comprehend the subject. By knowing the purpose of studying it, students can better grasp the concepts and principles of geometry. As Participant 8 stated that:

“Akong ma share sa uban na students na mag learn sa geometry is that ilang hibalo.ug unsa ang purpose sa geometry. If mahibaloan nila ang purpose mas mapadali ang pagsabot nila sa geometry.” (IDI-08)

(I want to share with other students who are learning geometry is that they should understand the purpose of geometry. If they understand its purpose, it will make it easier for them to comprehend geometry.)

Moreover, to students who are also studying geometry, it's crucial for them to understand the nature of geometry and where it can be applied. Knowing the practical applications of geometry helps students comprehend its significance and motivates them to study it further. Understanding where geometry can be applied in specific situations enhances their comprehension and motivation to delve deeper into the subject. As Participant 5 said that:

“Ang akong ma share sa other mathematics students na ga tuon pod sa geometry is that dapat makabalo jud sila ug studyhan jud nila ang nature sa geometry and asa pod sya maapply kay kung makabalo ka kung asa nmo sya magamit mas makabalo ka ba na or mas maging motivated ka na magstudy about sa geometry kay kabalo ka na maapply sya ana na specific na butang.” (IDI-05)

(What I want to share with other mathematics students who are also studying geometry is that they should really understand and study the nature of geometry and where it can be applied. Because if you know where it can be used, you'll understand better or you'll be more motivated to study about geometry because you know it can be applied to specific things.)

Lastly, It is important to note that, understanding and mastering the basics in geometry is crucial just like any other branch of mathematics. It shows that there is a need to focus on basic concepts instead of hastily reaching at conclusions since such conclusions can result in mistakes. Additionally, it means that approaches should be shared according to this tenet so that they have a firm grounding on the basics before they move on to more complex concepts. As Participant 8 cited that:

“Strategies lng gyud na akong ma share sa ilaha with regards sa geometry kay hinumdoman lng gyud ang basics. Basics lng gyud bisan unsa pa na branch sa mathematics. Dli ta magdali dali ug himo ug conclusion if naa ta particular na problem na dli ta magdali dali ug conclude kay dha man musulod ang kamalian nato.” (IDI-08)

(The only strategy I can share with them regarding geometry is to always remember the basics. Basics are essential no matter what branch of mathematics. We shouldn't rush to conclusions. If we encounter a specific problem, we shouldn't hastily jump to conclusions because that's where our mistakes can occur.)

Utilizing Online Platform is Necessary to Enhance Learning. This is the third code of the first issue probed. Incorporating online platforms into education is important for improving the learning experience. By using online platforms, students can access a wide range of educational materials. Additionally, online platforms offer flexibility and convenience, allowing learners to study at their own pace and access educational content from anywhere with an internet connection.

Consequently, when mathematics students encounter difficulty understanding geometry concepts through traditional face-to-face discussions, they can explore alternative learning strategies to improve their understanding. Students can seek for tutorial videos to supplement their learning and enhance comprehension of the concepts. This highlights the importance of flexibility and resourcefulness in finding effective methods for learning difficult subjects like geometry. As Participant 4 stated that:

“The strategies that I can share with other mathematics students sa paglearn sa geometry is if naa silay nalisoran na subject and dli nila masabtan through face- to-face discussion, pwede sila mangita ug ways para makatuon. For example, sa akoo na part na maglisod ug tuon in discussion face to face is naga tan.aw ko ug tutorial videos para mas masabtan nko ang concept.” (IDI-04)

(The strategies that I can share with other mathematics students in learning geometry is that if they encounter a difficult subject and cannot understand it through face- to-face discussion, they can explore other ways to learn. For example, when I find it challenging to grasp a concept through face-to-face discussions, I watch tutorial videos to better understand the concept.)

Moreover, self-learning plays a crucial role in acquiring knowledge. Utilizing online tutorials can be highly beneficial, as they provide additional resources and assistance that can enhance one's understanding of the subject matter. This emphasizes the importance of independent learning and using available online resources to supplement traditional classroom education. As participant 2 cited that:

“The strategies that I can share is aside from learning from your teacher is mag self-learning jud. Daghan mag tutorial online which is makahelp jud sa imohan na mas makatuon man jud kag maayo.” (IDI-02)

(The strategy I can share, aside from learning from your teacher, is to engage in self-learning. There are many online tutorials available that can truly help you learn more effectively.)

Lastly, when facing difficulties understanding certain topics, particularly in geometry, students turn to online resources for assistance. They prioritize researching online and spend time finding appropriate websites or tutorial videos on platforms like YouTube to enhance their understanding. This highlights the importance of using digital resources for self-directed learning and leveraging freely available online materials to supplement their studies effectively. As Participant 10 said that:

“The strategies that I usually use during my studies especially learning geometry is if in case there are topics I do not understand, first I do research online and I spend more time surfing on the internet to find the appropriate website that will help me understand the topic. If in case there are no website that are available, I go to YouTube for tutoring today videos because those websites are free sites that really help you in your studies.” (IDI-10)

Challenges in Learning Environment and Resources. Based from the qualitative data gathered from the in-depth interviews, students shared insights about the challenges in learning environment and resources in the institution. The participant's response's as being recorded implied that the status of learning environment and the availability of learning resources influence their attitude in learning.

Disruptive Learning Environment. This is the first code for the second probe issue. Disruptive learning environment affect the focus of students towards learning geometry which leads to confusion and poor understanding to the subject matter. Students collectively considered the status of learning environment as a factor of their attitudes towards learning geometry.

Consequently, the learning environment significantly influences students' ability to focus and learn effectively. In this specific case, the proximity of the classroom to a construction site results in excessive noise, which disrupts students' concentration and adversely affects their learning experience. As Participant 3 said that:

“Sa learning environment, ang among room kay duol sa construction site maong saba gyud sa and makaapekto gyud sa among pagtuon may dli mi maka focus.” (IDI-03)

(In the learning environment, our room is close to a construction site, so it's really noisy and it really affects our studying because we can't focus.)

Moreover, in a learning environment, particularly in the context of a geometry lesson involving matrices, students' attitudes can be significantly impacted. Working with matrices can be challenging for students, which can lead to a loss of focus. Additionally, factors such as discomfort due to weather conditions can further distract students from their learning. Therefore, creating a conducive and comfortable learning environment is crucial to help students stay focused and engaged in their studies, especially when dealing with complex topics like matrices. As Participant 8 cited that:

“Regarding sa learning environment didto sa part sa geometry lesson na matrix maka change jud sa attitude labi nag mag solve kag matrix nya banha lisod jud kaayo sa kay ang matrix numbers jud baya na sa, daghan kaayo na numbers, makawala sa focus. Isa pa dha ang kaigang, kainit sa panahon makawala pod na sa sa focus.” (IDI-08)

(In the learning environment, particularly in the geometry lesson involving matrices, it really changes one's attitude, especially when solving matrices. It becomes really difficult because matrices consist of numerous numbers, which can lead to a loss of focus. Furthermore, discomfort, such as the heat, also contributes to a lack of focus.)

Lastly, learning environment can significantly impact students' ability to focus and engage with the material. Factors such as discomfort due to room conditions, noise interference, and difficulty in seeing visual aids like PowerPoint presentations can hinder students' learning experiences. When students are uncomfortable or distracted, their ability to analyze and understand concepts is compromised. They may end up focusing more on trying to alleviate their discomfort rather than on learning. Additionally, excessive noise and interruptions make it difficult for teachers to effectively conduct discussions and for students to concentrate on the lesson. Therefore, creating a conducive and comfortable learning environment with minimal distractions is essential for effective teaching and learning. As participant 14 affirmed that:

“Ang rooms sometimes kay igang kaayo and there are noise interference sa palibot, ang classroom kay guot, unya ang ppt kay dli kaayo makita. Untahay kung igang kaayo, imbes na I focus niya ang hunahuna na mag analyze sa concept mas nagfocus sa ug pagpangita ug way na dli sa igangon kay syempre ulaw kaayo dba na mag singot ta. If saba kaayo dli nko madunggan akong teachers na magdiscuss. Pag guot pod kaayo kay dli kaayo comfortable kay daghan kaayog lihokan ug daghan kaayog interruptions sa palibot.” (IDI-14)

(The rooms sometimes get very cramped and there's a lot of noise interference around. The classroom feels cramped, and the PowerPoint presentations are not very visible. When it's too cramped, instead of focusing on analyzing the concept, one ends up focusing more on finding ways to alleviate the discomfort because, of course, it's very embarrassing, isn't it? If it's too noisy, I can't hear my teachers discussing. When it's too cramped, it's also uncomfortable because there are too many movements and interruptions around.)

Insufficient Learning Resources. This is the second code of the second probed issue. Insufficient learning resources can impede students' ability to learn geometry comprehensively and inhibit their academic achievement in the subject. Access to adequate resources is essential to create a supportive learning environment where students can explore, practice, and master geometric concepts effectively. The participants affirmed that insufficient learning resources affects their attitudes of students towards learning geometry.

Consequently, in the institution lacks sufficient resources to enhance students' learning experiences. While there is a library available, it is noted that the collection of books is inadequate, indicating a shortage of resources. Specifically, in the context of geometry education, there is a need for 3D models to better visualize geometric concepts, which are currently lacking. This suggests that the institution's resources are insufficient to support effective learning, particularly in subjects like geometry, where visual aids are crucial for comprehension and engagement. As Participant 5 stated that:

“My perception about the learning environment in the institution is kulang jud atong resources na mas maka learn pa ang mga students ba. Hinoon naa man tay library but dli gyud enough ang books na naa sa library kay naa pod juy kulang. And also sa geometry kay

needed jud kaayo and 3D models para mas makita gyud sa mga students like me kung unsa ka nindot ang geometry.” (IDI-05)

(My perception of the learning environment in the institution is that our resources are really lacking to further enhance students' learning. However, we do have a library, but the number of books available is not sufficient; there are also gaps. Especially in geometry, 3D models are really needed for students like me to better visualize the beauty of geometry.)

Moreover, the learning environment at the institution is generally acceptable, there are shortcomings when it comes to studying geometry, primarily due to insufficient resources. The lack of resources, particularly for measurement tools and devices needed for deeper exploration of geometry concepts, hampers the learning process. This underscores the limitations caused by inadequate resources in effectively teaching and learning geometry. As Participant 7 cited that:

“When it comes to learning environment, sa institution is ok lang but if mag focus ta about geometry medyo naa sya kakulangan. Ang kakulangan niya is more on resources. When it comes to study geometry daghan gyud kag need na mga gamit, for measurement and devices na pwede magamit if we learn deeper in geometry. Last time sa geometry namo we're having hard time ug asa magkuha ug informations kay wala mi ingon na gina follow na book. Ang among source lng kay sa internet, of course sa internet daghan ug information so magsagol sagol mostly naay maapil na dli diay sya need. Limited resources.” (IDI-07)

(When it comes to the learning environment, the institution is okay, but when we focus on geometry, there's a bit of a shortage. The shortage primarily lies in resources. Studying geometry requires a lot of tools for measurement and devices that can be used for deeper learning. Last time in our geometry class, we had a hard time finding information because we didn't have a specific book to follow. Our only source was the internet, and while there's a lot of information available online, most of it is irrelevant to what we actually need. So, there are limited resources.)

Lastly, learning environment in the institution is not very conducive, especially during the current season of heat, discomfort, and reduced mental agility. Additionally, there is a notable lack of resources and materials, particularly in terms of models, which are essential for visualizing 3D figures. The students highlight the need for better resources and materials to support effective learning, particularly in subjects like geometry where visualization is crucial. As Participant 9 affirmed that:

“Sa dri na institution na observe lng nako na ang learning environment dli kaayo sya ingon na conducive especially karon na panahon na init, igang, dili kaayo mugana ang utok. Tapos, ang resources ug materials naay kakulangan jud no especially sa mga models kasi during sa among time kami pa ang gipabuhay ug models sa among instructor para ma visualize jud namo ang figure sa 3D model.” (IDI-09)

(In this institution, I have observed that the learning environment is not very conducive, especially during this season of heat, discomfort, and reduced mental alertness. Additionally, there is a notable lack of resources and materials, especially when it comes to models. During our time, we had to make our own models under the guidance of our instructor to truly visualize the figures in 3D.)

Interactive Pedagogy in Geometry Learning. In response to the in-depth interviews, participants mentioned that Interactive pedagogy can have a significant impact on geometry learning by fostering deeper understanding, engagement, and retention of geometric concepts. Interactive teaching styles motivates students to become attentive in learning the subject.

Teachers' Efficiency in Teaching. This is the first code for the third probed issue. From the in-depth interviews, it is shared by many students that teachers' efficiency in teaching help mathematics major students to improve their geometry performance. The participants affirmed that teacher's efficiency contributes their attitudes of towards learning geometry.

Consequently, the students had a positive experience with teaching strategies in their institution. They found that their instructors were masters in their respective fields, which led to an enhanced learning experience. The students realized that what they had learned in high school was insufficient and needed improvement, but they saw significant upgrades and enhancements in their understanding due to the teaching strategies employed by the institution and the expertise of the instructors. This highlights the importance of effective teaching strategies and skilled instructors in improving and upgrading students' knowledge and learning experiences. As Participant 8 said that:

“About sa teaching strategies, okay man pod akong na experience, akong mga instructor's kay master man pod sa ilang field. So naka learn ko ug sapay ug sobra pa gani ug kadto akong na learn from high school is na upgrade jud sya. Nakaingon gyud ko na kulang diay tong na learn nko sa high school dri nako nakita na kulang gyud sya na kailangan pa ma improve, na improve sya gamay and kabalok ko na mas ma improve pani tungod sa mga teaching strategies dri sa institution ug tungod sa mga instructors na master sa ilang field.” (IDI-08)

(Regarding teaching strategies, I've had a good experience. My instructors are masters in their field. So, I've learned and even exceeded what I learned in high school. I realized that what I learned in high school was lacking and needed improvement. It has indeed improved, and I know it can further improve because of the teaching strategies in this institution and the instructors who are masters in their field.)

Moreover, the teaching strategies employed during the speaker's geometry classes have been highly effective. The students attribute their success in geometry, as evidenced by high grades received in their first and second years, to the engaging teaching methods used by their instructors. These methods include providing 3D examples, creating tutorial videos, and facilitating discussions during face-

to-face classes. Despite the complexity of the subject matter, the instructors effectively conveyed the lessons, leaving a lasting impact on the speaker. The speaker expresses gratitude to their teachers for laying a strong foundation in geometry, which they believe will benefit them in future mathematical pursuits, particularly in calculus, where geometry, trigonometry, and algebra are applied. As Participant 10 cited that:

“The teaching strategies that I’ve encountered while learning geometry is quite effective. I have seen it as a result when I was first year and during our first semester of our second year. Thankfully I’ve received high grades, it was really a very effective teaching style. One teacher really did a 3D example he also did a tutorial video and aside from that he also reinforces discussion during face-to-face classes. The other teachers as well is very good in this subject matter even though the subject is wordy. Nevertheless, they have really impacted on me the great lessons in geometry. I’m very thankful to them that they really build foundation for us in order for all of us mathematics students to be equipped in the next subject we will encounter, especially calculus because calculus is the application of geometry, trigonometry, and algebra.” (IDI-10)

(The teaching strategies I’ve encountered while learning geometry have been quite effective. I’ve seen this reflected in my grades during my first year and the first semester of my second year. Fortunately, I’ve received high grades; the teaching style was truly effective. One teacher provided a 3D example and created tutorial videos, in addition to facilitating discussions during face-to-face classes. The other teachers were also proficient in the subject matter, despite its complexity. They have had a significant impact on me with their excellent geometry lessons. I’m very grateful to them for laying a solid foundation for all mathematics students, especially as we move on to subjects like calculus, which involve the application of geometry, trigonometry, and algebra.)

Lastly, an effective teacher can greatly impact students’ attentiveness and learning efficiency. When a teacher is skilled at conveying information clearly and comprehensively, students are more likely to pay attention during class and grasp the material more quickly. This results in students spending less time on learning the same lessons independently, as they can understand the concepts after just one teaching session. Overall, the statement emphasizes the importance of teaching effectiveness in optimizing students’ learning experiences and outcomes. As Participant 11 stated that:

“If the teacher is really efficient in teaching, I’d likely to be more attentive in his or her class and I wouldn’t spend too much time on learning few lessons it’s because it’s already clear on one session of teaching.” (IDI-11)

Utilizing varied Strategies to cater Diverse Learners. This is the second code for the third probed issue. The participants affirmed that teachers utilizing varied strategies are effective as learners have diverse learning strategies. Varied teaching strategies will hit the interest of students and it will help them to grasp the concept of the lesson, especially geometry. In addition, it encourages and influences students specifically their attitude toward geometry learning.

Consequently, effective teaching by a skilled teacher result in increased attentiveness from students and quicker comprehension of lessons. When a teacher is efficient in their teaching methods, students are more engaged in class and find that they grasp the material more readily, often needing less time to study outside of class to understand the concepts thoroughly. This highlights the crucial role of teaching effectiveness in facilitating learning and maximizing students’ understanding of the subject matter. As Participant 11 said that:

“If the teacher is really efficient in teaching, I’d likely to be more attentive in his or her class and I wouldn’t spend too much time on learning few lessons it’s because it’s already clear on one session of teaching.” (IDI-11)

Moreover, while teachers are generally okay, they are not perfect, and there are areas where improvement is needed, especially in teaching geometry. Sometimes, there are lessons that teachers may not cover thoroughly, leaving students with doubts. It is essential for teachers to acknowledge their shortcomings and strive for improvement, particularly in subjects like geometry where the discussion directly relates to the topic. The speaker emphasizes the importance of teachers adopting a growth mindset and being open to different teaching strategies to accommodate diverse learning styles among students. They also stress the need for differentiated instruction and self-reflection on teaching methods and assessment results. Additionally, the speaker suggests offering remedial classes to help struggling students catch up and achieve the lesson objectives. Overall, the statement underscores the importance of continuous improvement and adaptability in teaching practices to ensure effective learning outcomes. As Participant 7 stated that:

“Teacher’s kay ok lang, as what I’ve experienced although naay kakulangan kay dili man gyud ingon na perfect ang teacher. Naay uban lesson na dili kaayo ma discuss sa teacher, kanang naay usahay ang student’s ma left in doubt. Si teacher dapat mudawat na naay kakulangan when it comes to learning geometry kay ang discussion kay mag touch lng jud sa geometry. Dapat jud naay improvement si teacher. Among na experience man gud namo last time na approach sa teacher when it comes teaching geometry kay authoritative. Ang teaching strategies dapat daghan kay lahi-lahi man pod ug learning styles ang students. Different teaching strategies, differentiated instructions, and you have to reflect on your teaching style and results sa imong assessments. If naglisod imong students you can create remedial class para maka cope up ug para ma meet nimo tong imong objectives sa lesson.” (IDI-07)

(Teachers are okay, as far as my experience goes, although there are shortcomings because no teacher is perfect. There are some lessons that the teacher may not discuss thoroughly, leaving students sometimes in doubt. The teacher should acknowledge that there are shortcomings when it comes to learning geometry because the discussion is solely focused on geometry. The teacher should really

strive for improvement. Our previous experience was that sometimes the teacher's approach to teaching geometry was authoritative. Teaching strategies should be diverse because students have different learning styles. Different teaching strategies, differentiated instructions, and you have to reflect on your teaching style and the results of your assessments. If your students are struggling, you can create a remedial class to help them cope and to meet the objectives of your lesson.)

Lastly, the students appreciate their geometry instructor's teaching strategies, particularly the approach of teaching step by step without assuming prior knowledge. The instructor acknowledges that students have different learning paces and ensures that each concept is explained thoroughly to facilitate understanding. This highlights the effectiveness of a patient, step-by-step teaching approach in promoting comprehension and retention of geometry concepts. As Participant 11 cited that:

“There are different definitely strategies but not really particular in geometry but I'm gladly like to present that our instructor in geometry really have these strategies teaching it step by step not assuming things that I can already do this. He assumes that everyone has a different phase of learning so he teaches it step by step so I can really understand the concept very well and I can't forget it that easy. Because if the teacher is too fast in explaining things and I have to recap again in my own and spend more time in studying other than learning it on the time the teacher is already teaching in front.” (IDI- 11)

(There are definitely different strategies, but not particularly in geometry. However, I'm pleased to say that our geometry instructor does employ these strategies, teaching step by step without assuming that I already know the material. He recognizes that everyone learns at a different pace, so he breaks it down step by step to ensure I understand the concept thoroughly and don't forget it easily. If the teacher were too fast, I'd have to review on my own and spend more time studying outside of class rather than learning it during the actual lesson.)

Employing Student-Centered Teaching Method. This is the third code for the third probed issue. Majority of the individuals tapped in the qualitative data collection have stated that employing student-centered teaching method greatly affect their attitude in learning geometry. In a reason that it allows students to be hands on in the learning process which helps them for better learning.

Consequently, the teaching strategies employed by the teachers are effective, particularly when they involve hands-on activities and projects rather than just lectures. The students highlight the effectiveness of activities such as presenting 3D models and engaging students in exploration outside of the classroom. They emphasize that geometry is not easily learned through lectures alone, and active participation from students is crucial for understanding. Additionally, the students mention the effectiveness of projects and exhibitions involving geometric shapes, which help reinforce understanding of geometric concepts such as angles and planes. This highlights the importance of interactive and engaging teaching methods in effectively teaching geometry. As Participant 6 said that:

“Ang maingon nako sa mga teaching strategies na gi apply sa atong mga maestra is effective sya no, let's say katong nagpa present silag 3D models. Ang example sa teaching strategies na gi apply sa akong maestra sa una kay naga pa activity sila like dli sila more on lectures like through activities mag explore-explore ug mga objects outside sa school is effective sya kay ang geometry man gud dli kayo sya dali matun.an pag ang maestra lng ang more on naga lecture, nagatudlo lng sila like more on yawyaw lng ang maestra so ang kana na specific na teaching strategy kanang magpa activity kay effective sya kay tungod ang student man ang mu engaged sa mismo sa geometry dli lng ang maestra. Isa pajud na effective is kanang magpa project ang maestra ug mga geometric shapes, exhibitions, kay makita man nato ba ug unsay ginapasabot anang mga terms sa geometry like mga angles ug mga planes“(IDI-06)

(What I can say about the teaching strategies applied by our teachers is that they are effective, especially when they present 3D models. An example of a teaching strategy used by my teacher before is conducting activities rather than relying solely on lectures. Through these activities, we explore objects outside of school, which is effective because geometry is not easily understood through lectures alone. When the teacher focuses more on lecturing, it can sometimes lead to disengagement from the students, as they are merely being talked at rather than actively participating. Another effective strategy is when the teacher assigns projects involving geometric shapes or exhibitions, as it helps us understand the meanings of geometric terms like angles and planes.)

Moreover, the teaching strategies encountered while learning geometry were highly effective. The students appreciate the instructor's approach, which involves providing hands-on experiences and allowing students to solve problems independently. They highlight the importance of experiencing real-world problems to apply what they have learned and gain a deeper understanding of the nature of geometry. Overall, the statement emphasizes the value of practical, experiential learning in effectively teaching geometry. As Participant 5 affirmed that:

“Akong ma ingon sa teaching strategies na akong na encounter while ga learn kog geometry is that nindot jud kaayo ang strategies na ginahatag sa among instructor dati kay gina pa experience niya sa amoa nga kami lang own na makatuon and also mag solve gyud mi. Hatagan mi niga ug real world problems para maapply namo kung unsa gyud among na learn also makasabot mi sa nature sa geometry. Mao na sya akong na experience na teaching strategy.” (IDI-05)

(What I can say about the teaching strategies I encountered while learning geometry is that the strategies provided by our instructor were really good. He made sure that we learned on our own and also solved problems ourselves. We were given real-world problems to apply what we learned and to understand the nature of geometry. That's the teaching strategy I experienced.)

Lastly, the students noticed a teacher-centered approach to teaching geometry in their first year. They believe it would be better if

students were more actively involved in their own learning process, such as by solving problems themselves or participating in activities that enhance their understanding of geometry. The students suggests that a more hands-on approach, where students take a more active role in their learning, would be more effective than a solely teacher-centered approach. As Participant 14 stated that:

“So naa man mi subject na geometry when I was in first year and nabantayan nko na teacher centered japon kaayo, unta ang institution ang teacher ra ang ga discuss unya wala kaayo ginahimo ang students and I think mas nndot if ang students jud mismo ang mag hands-on in terms of learning geometry like sila ang mag solve or there are ang certain activities na mag lead sa ilang knowledge sa geometry.” (IDI-14)

(So, we had geometry as a subject when I was in first year, and I noticed that it was still very teacher-centered. I wish the institution would have the students themselves actively participate in learning instead of just the teacher leading the discussion, with students not doing much. I believe it would be better if the students themselves were hands-on in learning geometry, like solving problems or engaging in certain activities that would enhance their understanding of geometry.)

Data Integration of the Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

The present study on the attitudes of students towards learning geometry carries out a mixed methods approach employing convergent parallel approach. The fourth research question of the study involves the corroboration of the findings from quantitative and qualitative phase. The table 6 on the salient quantitative and qualitative findings presents focal points in the first column which contains the variable of the study followed by the quantitative and qualitative findings in the second and third column. The findings from the quantitative phase are usually the indicators with the highest mean while the qualitative findings which displays the identified responses show confirmation or disconfirmation to the quantitative results. The fourth column is the nature of the data integration, and the fifth column contains the axiological implications made based on the data described in preceding columns.

Table 6. Joint Display of Salient Quantitative and Qualitative Findings

ASPECT OR FOCAL POINT	QUANTITATIVE FINDINGS	QUALITATIVE FINDINGS	NATURE OF DATA INTEGRATION	AXIOLOGICAL IMPLICATIONS
Attitudes in Learning Geometry	Table 1 on the indicator usefulness specifically item 1 about need geometry for my future (M=4.16), item 3 about often see geometry in everyday things (M=4.11); item 4 about need a firm understanding of geometry in my future work (M=4.21); item 5 about can see geometry as a practical subject to study (M=4.25), which are all rated as high.	Table 4 on the category - Understanding the Practical Role of Geometry under the theme - Having a favorable disposition towards learning geometry	Merging – converging	Mathematics major students recognize the usefulness of geometry as it is a practical subject to study and is essential for daily life and future careers.
	Table 1 on the indicator confidence specifically item 1-sure that I can learn geometry concepts. (M=4.24), item 4 about confident that if I work long enough on geometry problem, I will be	Table 4 on the category - confident in learning geometry under the theme - Having a favorable disposition towards learning geometry.	Merging – converging	Mathematics major students are confident in learning geometric concepts due to genuine interest in the subject which drives them to get high scores in assessments.

	able to solve it (M=4.17), and item 5 about have lot of confidence when it comes to studying geometry (M=3.96), all are rated as high.			
	Table 1 on the indicator enjoyment item 4 about enjoying solving geometry (M=4.13) which rated as high, item 3 about geometry is an interesting subject to study (M=4.26), and item 5 about geometry has many interesting topics to study (M=4.33) which both are rated as very high.	Table 4 on the category - enjoyment in learning geometry under the theme - Having a favorable disposition towards learning geometry	Merging - Converging	Mathematics major students are enjoying towards learning as it has many interesting topics to study and by exploring the relevance of geometry in daily life.

Attitudes in Learning Geometry. In the quantitative phase, the specific item under the indicator usefulness rated as high about seeing geometry as a practical subject to study. Also, the items about needing a firm understanding of geometry in my future work, about needing geometry for my future, and about often seeing geometry in everyday things, are both rated as high. This result relates to the qualitative findings on the category practical role of geometry under the theme having a favorable disposition towards learning geometry. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Moreover, In the quantitative phase, the specific item under the indicator confidence rated as high about being sure that I can learn geometry concepts. Also, the items about being confident that if I work long enough on geometry problem, I will be able to solve it, and having lot of confidence when it comes to studying geometry, are both rated as high. This result relates to the qualitative findings on the category confident in learning geometry under the theme having a favorable disposition towards learning geometry. Hence, the qualitative data converges quantitative in this aspect.

Furthermore, In the quantitative phase, the specific item under the indicator enjoyment rated as very high is about saying geometry has many interesting topics to study. Also, the item about saying geometry is an interesting subject to study which rated as very high. Thus, about enjoying solving geometry which rated as high. This result relates to the qualitative findings on the category enjoyment in learning geometry under the theme having a favorable disposition towards learning geometry. It is then safe to say that the qualitative data converges quantitative.

Conclusions

The study findings led to the following conclusions: First, the status of students' geometry attitude is high in terms of usefulness, confidence, and enjoyment. This indicates that mathematics teacher education students consistently exhibit strong indicators of geometry attitude. The students find learning geometry useful in everyday life and future careers. Also, the students show confidence in learning geometry. Thus, the students find enjoyment in learning geometry.

Second, a thematic analysis of the qualitative data, derived from in-depth interview (IDI), offered deeper insights into the lived experiences of mathematics education students. This analysis highlighted the status of students' attitudes towards learning geometry and revealed favorable strategies for learning geometry. The qualitative findings provided a richer understanding of the status and challenges faced by mathematics education students toward learning geometry. The following themes emerged: Having a Favorable Disposition Towards Learning Geometry, Utilizing Interactive Teaching to Boost Learning, and Support System's Impact on Boosting Learning. This indicates that mathematics education students have positive attitudes towards learning geometry. Thus, utilizing interactive teaching strategies as well as the impact of support systems boosts students' learning geometry.

Third, from the participants' responses, other themes are identified which show the insights shared of mathematics teacher education

students with regards to attitudes towards learning geometry. The following are the themes: Improving Geometry Learning with Collaboration and Digital Tools, Challenges in Learning Environment and Resources, and Interactive Pedagogy in Geometry Learning. This indicates that geometry learning will improve through collaboration of learners and with the aid of digital tools. Also, a comfortable and engaging learning environment and availability of learning resources are important in mathematics learning, especially in learning geometry. Thus, having an interactive pedagogy in geometry is important as it will enhance students' engagement towards the subject.

Lastly, to better understand the attitudes of students toward learning geometry, the responses were analyzed thematically to confirm the quantitative results of the study. Both the findings from the two phases are integrated based on the nature plan. The status of geometry attitude based on the quantitative results shows that it converged to the data gained from the qualitative phase. Both quantitative and qualitative results confirm that students verify the usefulness of learning geometry, the students have confidence in learning geometry, and the students enjoy learning geometry. This indicates that mathematics education students in local college, specifically in Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology, has positive attitudes in learning geometry.

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were being drawn:

Since the status of the geometry attitude reveals that among the three indicators of geometry attitude, confidence has the lowest mean which affects how students learn their lesson the least, it is recommended that teachers should use visual aids such as geometric shapes and manipulatives and relate them to real-world applications in architecture and daily life to boost students' confidence in their ability to learn geometry. Divide geometric problem-solving into simple steps so students can tackle obstacles one at a time. To encourage investigation, provide students with open-ended activities that excite their curiosity and foster critical thinking. Encourage peer cooperation to promote shared understanding and provide constructive criticism and appreciation to reinforce learning achievements. Additionally, to suit diverse learning styles, provide a variety of learning resources, such as interactive apps and textbooks. Thus, to enhance knowledge and confidence in their capacity to learn geometry, students should reflect on their progress and review topics as needed. These activities will help students gain confidence in their ability to understand geometry.

Moreover, based on the qualitative phase results on the lived experiences of mathematics teacher education students in terms of their attitudes towards learning geometry, educators may emphasize the practical applications of geometry in fields such as architecture and engineering, incorporate hands-on activities and problem-solving sessions to boost confidence, use interactive tools to make learning enjoyable, and provide personalized feedback and positive reinforcement. These approaches seek to instill in students awareness for geometry's use, boost their confidence in learning geometric concepts, and promote a sense of delight and curiosity in the subject.

Further, those differentiated insights shared of mathematics teacher education students with regards to their attitudes towards learning geometry may be used to meet their learning needs. Also, new strategies may form for students to utilize and to have positive attitude towards learning the subject as the advancement of technology happens constantly, meaning there may be new ways to use in learning as technology upgrades and becomes more useful to students.

Furthermore, the researcher recommends the utilization of ICT tools such as interactive geometry software like GeoGebra or Desmos, virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) applications, online collaborative platforms such as Google Classroom, multimedia resources including videos and interactive simulations, and digital assessment tools can significantly enhance students' understanding of geometry by providing dynamic visualizations and hands-on exploration opportunities.

Lastly, it is also being recommended that the students develop a strong grasp of geometry and cultivate a keen interest in learning the subject, students may regularly practice geometric problems, use extra learning materials like books and online resources, solve real-life geometry problems to see its practical uses, and stay curious and persistent when facing difficulties. This approach will help them build confidence and develop a positive attitude towards geometry.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Julius Clyde C. Cabig

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines

Linagyn A. Gementiza-Cubio, LPT

Kapalong College of Agriculture Sciences and Technology – Philippines